

USAGE OF *CICHORIUM INTYBUS* IN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE, PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND IMPORTANCE IN PHARMACOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The common mushroom plant has been widely used in the Central Asian region of Kazakhstan in OIST disease, fever, inflammation and as a thirst quencher. There is a lot of sachratki glycoside and inulin in sachratki root. In European countries, it can be seen that the roots of Cichorium intybus are used in digestive diseases and to improve the digestion of food. Appetite is restored, digestion is improved. In Afghanistan, this plant was used in the treatment of various parasitic diseases, and these properties are scientifically based today.

Keywords: *Cichorium intybus, phytochemical composition, pharmacology, parasitic diseases, Cichorium balearicum Porta, Cichorium byzantinum Clementi, Cichorium caeruleum Gilib.*

Introduction: The original homeland of the plant is Asia, North Africa and Europe. The history of the plant's use dates back to ancient Egypt. In ancient Rome, various dishes were prepared from this plant. Horace wrote about this in his memoirs, "Olives, mint and peppermint give me strength." In 1766, Frederick the Great banned the importation of coffee into Prussia, and now people began to use Cichorium intybus as a substitute for coffee. Based on this, in 1769 and 1770, these products began to be produced in Berlin and Prussia. Lord Monbodeau in 1779 describes the plant as "chicoree", which the French cultivated as a pot herb. In France during the Napoleonic era, sachratki often appeared as a substitute for coffee. During the American Civil War, hops were adopted by Confederate soldiers as a substitute for coffee and became popular in the United States. It was also used in Great Britain during World War II, where Camp Coffee, a combination of coffee and hops, was sold since 1885.

Literature analysis and methodology on the topic:

In the United States, burdock root has long been used as a substitute for coffee in prisons. By the 1840s, the Port of New Orleans was the second largest importer of coffee. After Union naval blockades cut off the port of New Orleans during the American Civil War, Louisianans began adding the root to their coffee, creating a long-lasting tradition. *Cichorium intybus* can be found in all states of North America, USA. The collections collected in Canada show that there were originally nine local populations of the plant, 20 wild species in North America and 592 species and populations distributed in Eurasia. In addition to *Cichorium intybus*, *Cichorium balearicum* Porta, *Cichorium byzantinum* Clementi, *Cichorium caeruleum* Gilib, *Cichorium cicorea* Dumort, *Cichorium commune* Pall, *Cichorium cosnia* Buch.-Ham, *Cichorium divaricatum* Heldr. ex Nyman, *Cichorium glabratum* C. Presl, *Cichorium glaucum* Hoffmanns. Link, *Cichorium hirsutum* Gren, *Cichorium illyricum* borb, *Cichorium officinale* Gueldenst.Ledeb, *Cichorium perenne* Stokes, *Cichorium rigidum* Salisb., *Cichorium spinosum* Salisb., *Cichorium sylvestre* Garsault, *Cichorium sylvestre* Lam.

Result Discussion:

From Eurasia, Scandinavia to the Mediterranean Sea and the British Isles, it can be found in Eastern Siberia and the Southern parts of India, and in the Northern parts of Africa. It can be found in the European part of Russia, the Caucasus and Siberia.

The common mushroom plant has been widely used in the Central Asian region of Kazakhstan in OIST disease, fever, inflammation and as a thirst quencher. There is a lot of sachratki glycoside and inulin in sachratki root. This plant is valued as a plant of medicinal value in many countries of Eurasia and Africa. However, due to its widespread distribution on the earth, all parts of the plant are widely used in traditional medicine. Important phytochemical substances are distributed in the plant, and it can be seen that the largest part of them is located in the roots of the plant. Since ancient times, people have widely used medicinal plants and began to have accurate information about their medicinal properties as a result of various experiments, and this information was passed down from generation to generation. Historically, the mushroom plant was first used by the Egyptians, and the regions where it was spread were identified. As a result, various preparations have been made from this plant and presented in a convenient way for use. For example, it is used to treat wounds in Turkey. In some countries, its tinctures are used. In European countries, it can be seen that the roots of *Cichorium intybus* are used in digestive diseases and to improve the digestion of food. Appetite is restored, digestion is improved. In Afghanistan, this plant was used in the treatment of various parasitic diseases, and these properties are scientifically based today. And in Italy, sources have arrived that are mainly used as

tinctures. In India, *Cichorium intybus* is widely used among the population as a remedy for various liver diseases. In Bosnia and Greece, Serbia, and India, the roots of this plant are widely used in traditional medicine.

Conclusion

The phytochemical composition of this plant and its importance in pharmacology have been widely studied. The reason for this is that the medicinal properties of the plant depend on its chemical composition. Based on this, more than 100 chemical compounds have been isolated from the plant, and they mainly belong to the root of the plant.

In many regions of *Pakistan*, tinctures made from the root of the mushroom are used in diabetes. In this case, the roots are dried in the shade and ground into a powder. This powder is used twice a day with a glass of water before meals in order to reduce the level of glucose.

The research conducted in *West Azerbaijan* proved that local plants are of great importance for the health of the population. In the territory of Azerbaijan, the whole body parts of *Cichorium intybus* are used in the treatment of digestive problems, stomach pain, and removal of waste from the digestive tract. It is used to lower blood pressure and improve bile secretion.

In *Iran*, the roots and stems of this plant are used to improve the secretion of bile, to treat the liver, and in animes. It has been shown to be used for the treatment of influenza with the help of a powder made from the root.

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